

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS ON STEROLS, BILE ACID, HORMONE, ETC.
PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF 9-KETO-2 : 13-DIMETHYL- $\Delta^{10,1}$: 2-CYCLOPENTANO-
PERHYDROPHENANTHRENE

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A synthesis of cyclopentanoperhydrophenanthrene derivative with the angular methyl groups in proper position has been described. Possibility of the formation of vitamin-D₂ ring system from the above perhydrophenanthrene derivative has also been indicated.

During a study of two addition products of vitamin-D₂, Windaus and Thiele (*Annalen*, 1935, 521, 160) observed that dihydro derivatives of the above adducts, obtained by the saturation of the double bond in the side chain, on ozonisation yielded a saturated ketone of the composition C₁₉H₃₁O [VIII, R = -CH(CH₃)-CH₂.CH₂.-CH(CH₃)-CH(CH₃)-CH₂]. Later Dimroth and Jonsson (*Ber.*, 1941, 74B, 520) also obtained a stereoisomer of the same ketone by a different method. In view of the recent methods developed by different workers (Aldersley, Burkhardt, Gillam and Hindley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 10; cf. Aldersley and Burkhardt, *ibid.*, 1938, 545; Milas and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2534; Dimroth *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1942, 75B, 180, 322, 326, 510, 582, 1263; *ibid.*, 1943, 76B, 317) for the building up of ring systems possessing conjugated double bonds peculiar to vitamin-D₂ and D₃, the importance of the synthesis of the type of ketone (VIII) can hardly be over-estimated (*cf.* Barchmann and Struve, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1262, 2589). As a preliminary study we have carried out the synthesis of 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-one (VIII, R=H) by the following method.

Potassio or sodio derivative of ethyl 2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentylcyanoacetate has been condensed with ethyl β -bromopropionate and the resulting ethyl β -carbethoxy-ethyl-(2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentyl)cyanoacetate (I) is hydrolysed by prolonged refluxing with concentrated hydrochloric acid to yield α -(2-methyl-2-carboxycyclopentyl)-glutaric acid (II, R=H). Triethyl ester (II, R=Et) smoothly undergoes Dieckmann's condensation in presence of metallic sodium to give ethyl 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-7-one-4 : 6-dicarboxylate (III). For the subsequent hydrolysis, the above β -ketonic ester is refluxed in the crude state with 20% sulphuric acid and the resulting 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-7-one-4-carboxylic acid (IV), on purification by distillation in vacuum, solidified. The keto-acid (IV) is next reduced by refluxing with zinc amalgam and concentrated hydrochloric acid. 8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-carboxylic acid (V), thus obtained, is converted through its acid chloride, followed by bromination and esterification, into ethyl 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-bromo-4-carboxylate (VI). The above bromo-ester, on being refluxed with alcoholic potash, yields 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane- Δ^4 -ene-4-carboxylic acid (VII) as an oil. 8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-one (VIII, R=H) is obtained by treatment of this unsaturated acid with sodium azide and sulphuric acid in chloroform solution according to the method of Oesterlin (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1932, 45, 536; cf. Von Braun, *Annalen*, 1931, 490, 125).

Among the different methods developed for the preparation of vitamin- D_2 type of compound, mentioned above, few were successful in incorporating the required conjugated system. We, however, considered that a synthesis of the ergosterol nucleus (X) should furnish us with the parent substance, which might easily be converted into vitamin- D_2 type of compounds by irradiation, just as ergosterol and dehydrocholesterol are converted into vitamin- D_2 and D_3 respectively (Lette, *Annalen*, 1934, 511, 280; Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1631; Windaus and Langer, *Annalen*, 1933, 508, 105; Windaus, Lette and Schenck, *Annalen*, 1935, 520, 98; Windaus, Schenck and Werder, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1936, 241, 100; Grab, *ibid.*, 1936, 243, 63). With this end in view we have condensed 8-methyl-0:3:4-bicyclononane-4-one with methyl acetylcyclohexene in presence of potassium isopropylate in pyridine solution (Hüber, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 725) and 9-keto-2:13-dimethyl- Δ^9 :1:2-cyclopentano-perhydrophenanthrene (IX) is obtained in 40% yield as a yellow oil with characteristic odour. It is our intention to convert (IX) into the ergosterol nucleus following the reaction indicated below. Further work is also in progress to prepare the ketone of the type (VIII) with the *isooctyl* side chain in the proper position.

From our previous experience (Banerjee, *Science & Culture*, 1944, 9, 456; Bagchi and Banerjee, to be published in Part V later) it seems that the locking of the rings C and D is *cis*. Previously Linstead *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2014) have shown that the perhydrophenanthrene derivative (XI), obtained by the condensation of cyclohexanone and acetylcyclohexene, followed by catalytic reduction, possesses *trans-anti-trans* configuration *i.e.*, that present in the cholestane system. From the analogy of reaction, it is probable that the rings A, B and C in the tetracyclic ring system (IX) possess similar configuration at C₁₂, C₁₃ and C₁₄.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl β-Carboethoxyethyl-(2-methyl-2-carboethoxycyclopentyl)-cyanoacetate.—(a) Ethyl 2-methyl-2-carboethoxycyclopentylcyanoacetate (74.5 g., Bagchi and Banerjee, Part V, under publication) was slowly dropped into a cooled solution of sodium ethoxide from sodium (6.5 g.) and absolute alcohol (100 c.c.). The mixture was allowed to stand for a few hours and then to it in the cold was added ethyl β-bromopropionate (53 g.) and was left overnight. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 hours and was worked up in the usual way. The condensation product, which was obtained as a viscous oil, boiled at 195-97°/4-5 mm., yield 76 g., while unreacted cyano-ester (14.5 g.) was recovered. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 7.8. C₁₉H₂₉O₆N requires C, 62.1; H, 7.9 per cent).

(b) Ethyl 2-methyl-2-carboethoxycyclopentylcyanoacetate (13 g.) was slowly dropped in cooled dry xylene (50 c.c.) containing potassium dust (1.8 g.) and left overnight. Ethyl

β -bromopropionate (9 g.) was added to it in the cold and the whole was refluxed in an oil-bath for 20 hours, yield of the condensation product was 13 g.

Ethyl α -(2-Methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentyl)-glutarate.—The above condensation product (118 g.) was hydrolysed by prolonged refluxing with an excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid as before (Bagchi and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*). A small portion of the tricarboxylic acid crystallised out on cooling and was purified by recrystallisation from dilute hydrochloric acid (charcoal) when it melted at 189-92°. (Found : C, 55.9; H, 7.12. $C_{12}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.99 per cent). Main bulk of the acid solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath in a basin and the crude product mixed with ammonium chloride was esterified by the alcohol-sulphuric acid method. It was worked up in the usual way, when the tricarboxylic ester (76 g.) was obtained boiling at 175-176°/6 mm. On re-esterification of the acidic product obtained from the alkaline wash, further 17.5 g. of the tricarboxylic ester were obtained. (Found : C, 62.87; H, 8.87. $C_{18}H_{30}O_6$ requires C, 63.15; H, 8.78 per cent).

Ethyl 8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-7-one-4 : 6-dicarboxylate.—Tricarboxylic ester (II, R=Et; 32 g.) was refluxed in benzene solution with sodium dust (4.3 g.) until whole of the metallic sodium disappeared (*ca.* 3 hours). On working up in the usual manner, 18 g. of ethyl 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-7-one-4 : 6-dicarboxylate were obtained, b.p. 200°/12 mm. It gave an intense ferric chloride coloration in an alcoholic solution. (Found : C, 65.10; H, 8.34. $C_{16}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 64.86; H, 8.1 per cent).

8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-7-one-4-carboxylic Acid.—For the hydrolysis of the above β -ketonic ester, Dieckmann product obtained from 76 g. of the tricarboxylic ester (II, R=Et) after complete removal of solvents, was hydrolysed by refluxing with 500 c.c. of 20% sulphuric acid for 16 hours. After extraction with ether, the solvent was removed and the product was purified by distillation in vacuum (b.p. 182°/5 mm.) when it solidified, m.p. 95-96°, yield 30-32 g. (Found : C, 66.7; H, 8.2. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 8.2 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from dilute alcohol and melted at 217°. (Found : C, 56.7; H, 7.4. $C_{12}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires C, 56.9; H, 7.5 per cent).

8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-carboxylic Acid.—8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-7-one-4-carboxylic acid (40 g.) was heated under a reflux condenser with zinc amalgam (400 g., Bachmann, Carmack and Safir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1683) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) and toluene (10 c.c.) for 30 hours with addition (8 times) of further hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) at regular interval. The cold reaction mixture was thoroughly extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and ether removed. On fractionation, 28 g. of a product boiled at 156-158°/8 mm. (Found : C, 71.8; H, 9.6. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 72.5; H, 9.9 per cent).

8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane- Δ^4 -ene-4-carboxylic Acid.—8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-carboxylic acid (27 g.) was converted into its acid chloride by refluxing with thionyl chloride (27 c.c.) and dry benzene (50 c.c.) for 4 hours. Excess of thionyl chloride and benzene were removed under reduced pressure, and the residue on distillation in

vacuum boiled at 112-14°/7 mm., yield 29 g. It was then transferred to a flask with a little carbon tetrachloride and was then heated on a water-bath under a reflux condenser with the addition of a pinch of red phosphorus and bromine (10 c.c.) until the colour of bromine almost disappeared. Absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) was very cautiously added to the reaction mixture in the cold, with frequent swirling and then the whole was refluxed for 2 hours. On cooling, the alcoholic solution was poured into water and the heavy oil, which separated at the bottom, was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, soda solution and again with water. Ether was removed, and on distillation, ethyl 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-bromo-4-carboxylate (34 g.) boiled at 142-44°/8 mm. (Found : C, 53.4 ; H, 6.9. $C_{15}H_{21}O_2Br$ requires C, 53.99 ; H, 7.2 per cent).

The above bromo-ester was next refluxed with an alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (40 g. in 200 c.c. alcohol) for 4 hours, poured into a basin and the alcohol was removed on a boiling water-bath with the addition of distilled water. The cooled alkaline solution was acidified after it was extracted with ether. The acidic product was thoroughly extracted with ether. After removal of ether the residue boiled at 161°/8 mm., yield 18 g. (Found : C, 72.0 ; H, 8.8. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.3 ; H, 8.9 per cent). The product showed the presence of a trace of bromine by Berstein's test.

8-Methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-one.—The unsaturated ketone (VII, 17 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) and dry chloroform (80 c.c.) were taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury-sealed stirrer. Through one of the necks passed a thermometer fitted with a cork, while the third one was provided with a calcium chloride guard tube. Sodium azide (8 g.) was added in small portions at such a rate that the temperature of the reaction mixture remained between 40° and 50°. Stirring was continued even after the addition was complete until the frothing that occurred during the reaction completely subsided. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and refluxed for 2 hours, after replacing the guard tube with an upright condenser. On cooling, it was thoroughly extracted with ether, and the ethereal layer was washed with water, soda solution and with water again. Ether was removed and the residue on distillation boiled at 92-94°/8 mm. leaving a small quantity of a higher boiling product, yield 6 g. (Found : C, 78.2 ; H, 10.4. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.9 ; H, 10.5 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 185-86°. (Found : C, 63.10 ; H, 9.16. $C_{11}H_{16}ON_3$ requires C, 63.16 ; H, 9.09 per cent).

9-Keto-2 : 13-dimethyl- Δ^{10} -1 : 2-cyclopentano-perhydrophenanthrene.—Potassium dust (1.9 g.) under dry ether (50 c.c.) was treated with dry isopropyl alcohol (11.2 c.c.) in the cold, when a clear solution resulted within a short time. The ethereal solution of potassium isopropylate was cooled in an ice-bath and to it was added dropwise a solution of 8-methyl-0 : 3 : 4-bicyclononane-4-one (5.9 g.), methylacetylcyclohexene (5.3 g. ; Ruzicka, Koolhass and Dind, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, 14, 1151) in dry pyridine (20 c.c.) and the solution was left in a closed flask for 2 days. After refluxing for 1 hour the cooled solution was treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and was thoroughly extracted with ether. After removal of ether, the residue was fractionated when 3 g. of a product boiled

at 153-57° below 1 mm. and 6.3 g. of unreacted products were recovered. (Found : C, 82.7; H, 10.5. $C_{19}H_{25}O$ requires C, 83.8; H, 10.3 per cent).

A saturated aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate and the above unsaturated ketone were made clear with the addition of absolute alcohol and warming and left at the room temperature for several days, when the crystals of semicarbazone separated out slowly. These were collected, washed with water and then crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 164-66° (shrinks at 158°). (Found : C, 72.8; H, 9.3. $C_{20}H_{31}ON_3$ requires C, 72.9; H, 9.4 per cent).

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